
Research Article

Forest Health Analysis, Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques: A Case Study of
Omo Forest Reserve, Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

With climate change mitigation becoming a global issue in recent times, it has become imperative to monitor the health status of our forest reserves. It is also pertinent to state that there has been a high rate of fragmentation of the forest because of anthropogenic activities. The advancement in geospatial technologies coupled with archived spatio-temporal data, the monitoring of forest health has become very achievable. Landsat 8 (OLI-TIR) satellite image was used to generate vegetation indices which were further subjected to weighted sum overlay analysis to generate a comprehensive health status of the forest. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to assess the health status of the Omo forest reserve. The map was reclassified into four categories, i.e. non-forest, unhealthy, moderately healthy and very healthy. Non-forest covered about 6 % of the study area. Unhealthy forest occupied an area of about 25 %. The moderately healthy forest spanned across an area of about 44 % of the study area. Lastly, the very healthy forest occupied about 25 %. The Strict Natural Reserve (Omo Biosphere) happens to be part of the very healthy forest.

Keywords: Forest Health, Vegetation Indices, Remote Sensing, GIS

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Introduction

The perceived condition of a forest predicated on factors such as age, structure, composition, function, vigour, the presence of unusual levels of insects or diseases, and resilience to disturbance can be termed forest health (Martin and Aber, 2006). A forest is adjudged to be vigorous if the physical and biotic resources support productive forests, guarantee the sustenance of organisms within the ecosystem and the maintenance of a functional equilibrium between supply and demand of essential resources (Haile et al., 2014). Indicators commonly used in forest health monitoring include tree mortality, tree crown condition, the growth of trees (as shown by basal area, height or volume changes through time), plant diversity, the dominance of native species, soil Morphology and chemistry (Morse et al., 2005).

Healthy canopies of green vegetation have a very distinctive interaction with energy in the visible and near infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. In the visible regions, plant pigments (most notable chlorophyll) cause strong absorption of energy, primarily for photosynthesis. This absorption peaks in the red and blue areas of the visible spectrum, thus leading to the characteristic green appearance of most leaves. In the near infrared, however, a very different interaction occurs. The energy in this region is not used in photosynthesis, and it is strongly scattered by the internal structure of most leaves, leading to a very high apparent reflectance in the near infrared. It is this strong contrast, then, most particularly between the amount of reflected energy in the red and near-infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum, which has been the focus of a large variety of attempts to develop quantitative indices of vegetation condition using remotely sensed imagery (Eastman, 2012). The spectral characteristics of vegetation vary with wavelength. Chlorophyll absorbs radiation in the red and blue wavelengths, but reflects green wavelength. The internal structure of healthy leaves acts as a diffuse reflector of near-infrared wavelengths. Spectral bands are often used both individually and in combination with other bands to obtain vegetation indices (Berra et al. 2014 and Goergen et al. 2016).

The biometrical properties of vegetation in different wavelengths of the electromagnetic spectrum can be analyzed as well used for modeling and simulating biophysical processes (Salami and Balogun, 2006, Samvedan 2007, Jarocinska and Zagajewski, 2006). The most common vegetation index in forest classification and land cover change studies is NDVI. It reportedly improves vegetation classifications by partially compensating for variation in illumination due to terrain (Tucker, 1979, Lillesand and Kiefer, 1994). The main objective of this study is to analysis the forest health status of Omo Forests Reserve using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI),

Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI), Structure Insensitive Pigment Index (SIPI) and The Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI), using the instrumentalities of reclassification and weighted sum overlay analysis.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The Omo Forest Reserve is located between latitudes $6^{\circ} 35'$ to $7^{\circ} 05'$ N and longitudes $4^{\circ} 19'$ to $4^{\circ} 40'$ E around Ijebu axis of Ogun State in South western Nigeria (Figure 1). Omo covers about 130, 500 hectares, which includes a 460 ha Strict Natural Reserve (Okali and Ola-Adams, 1987), plus about 6, 500 ha of enclaves and cut out areas with a total of about 20,000 inhabitants (Dike, 1992). It lies within the tropical lowland rainforest. The climate is characterized by high temperatures, which range from 32.15°C to 21.40°C and a minimum relative humidity of 76.34%. It supports about 8000 species of plant. (Akinyemi et al., 2004). The mean annual rainfall ranges from about 1600 to 2000 mm with two annual peaks in June and September, with November and February are being the driest months (Lowe, 1993 and Hall, 1977).

Figure 1: Map of the study area.

Data used and source

Landsat 8 satellite image (OLI-TIR) of the study area acquired on the 13th March 2018 was obtained from USGS Earth Explorer official website. It covers 190/055 path/roll.

Table 1: Landsat 8 (OLI-TIR) bands and their wavelengths

BANDS	DESCRIPTION	WAVELENGTH[um]	RESOLUTION[m]
1	Coastal aerosol	0.43 - 0.45	30
2	Blue	0.45 - 0.51	30
3	Green	0.53 - 0.59	30
4	Red	0.64 - 0.67	30
5	Near Infrared	0.85 - 0.88	30
6	SWIR 1	1.57 - 1.65	30
7	SWIR	22.11 - 2.29	30
8	Panchromatic	0.50 - 0.68	15
9	Circus	1.36 - 1.38	30
10	Thermal Infrared 1	10.60 - 11.19	100
11	Thermal Infrared 2	11.50 - 12.51	100

Software used (Agbor et al, 2012, and Shao et al, 2017)

- (i) ArcGIS 10.5 software (ESRI) was used to generate various thematic layers.
- (ii) Idrisi Selva (Clark Lab) was used to do all raster related image analysis.

Methodology

Image processing

Geometric rectification is critical for producing spatially corrected map of land use/cover changes through time. The Landsat OLI images were in UTM projection (Zone 31N) on WGS84. Therefore, the images of the study area were geometrically corrected. Since the reflectance values will be necessary for the calculation of vegetation indices, the digital numbers (DN) must be converted to radiance and then to reflectance (Chukwuka and Funmilayo, 2018)

Converting DNS TO RADIANCE VALUES

$$L_{\lambda} = Ml * Q_{cal} + Al \tag{1}$$

Where:

L_{λ} = spectral radiance (w/(m²*Sr.µm))

Ml = Radiance multiplicative scaling factor for the band.

Al = Radiance additive scaling factor for the band.

Q_{cal} = L_i pixel value in DN

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Converting RADIANCE to TOA REFLECTANCE

$$P\rho = \frac{\bar{\lambda} \cdot L\lambda \cdot d^2}{ESUN\lambda \cdot \cos^2 \theta_s} \quad (2)$$

Where:

$P\rho$ = Unit less planetary reflectance

$L\lambda$ = Spectral Radiance at sensor's aperture

d^2 = Earth-sun distance in astronomical units:

$ESUN\lambda$ = Mean solar exo-atmospheric irradiances

θ_s = Solar zenith angle which is calculated using the equation

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) Calculation (Rouse et al. 1974)

The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index is widely used to monitor the vigor of vegetation canopy. NDVI was calculated using band 5 and band 4 of Landsat 8 with the aid of spectral index tools. This index is a measure of healthy, green vegetation. It's the use of the highest absorption and reflectance regions of chlorophyll make it very important (Oyundari, 2008, Makinde and Salami, 2014). It ranges between -1 to 1. The algorithm is stated below.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED} \quad (3)$$

Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI) Calculation (Gitelson and Merzlyak. 1995)

This index has a lot in common with NDVI. The major difference is that it measures the green spectrum from 540 to 570nm instead of the RED spectrum. This index is also unique because it is very sensitive to chlorophyll concentration.

$$GNDVI = \frac{NIR-GREEN}{NIR+GREEN} \quad (4)$$

Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI) Calculation (Kaufman and Tanre, 1992)

ARVI - (Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index) is an enhancement to the NDVI that is relatively resistant to atmospheric factors (for example, aerosol). It uses blue reflectance to correct red reflectance for atmospheric scattering. It is most useful in regions of high atmospheric aerosol content, including tropical regions contaminated by soot from slash-and-burn agriculture. The formula is

$$ARVI = \frac{NIR-2*RED-BLUE}{NIR+2*RED-BLUE} \quad (5)$$

Structure Insensitive Pigment Index (SIPI) Calculation (Harper et al 2005):

SIPI (Structure Insensitive Pigment Index) is a reflectance measurement designed to maximize the sensitivity of the index to the ratio of bulk carotenoids. An increase in SIPI values pre-supposes that there is an increase in canopy stress (a carotenoid pigment). It can very useful in the monitoring of vegetation health monitoring and plant stress analysis. The value of this index ranges from 0 to 2. The relevant bands are Band 5(NIR), 4 (RED) and Band 2 (BLUE).SIPI is defined by the following equation.

$$SIPI = \frac{NIR-BLUE}{NIR-RED} \tag{6}$$

Reclassification Weighted Overlay:

Each Vegetation index was reclassified using reclassify tool of the spatial analyst in ArcGIS. The reclassified vegetation indices were subjected to an overlay analysis to create a forest health map. The weighted sum function of the overlay tool in spatial analyst tool of ArcGIS is used. The four vegetation indices constituted the input data for the overlay analysis. This output was further reclassified into four different classes.

Results and Discussions

To spectrally analyze the forest health status of the Omo Forest Reserve, four relevant vegetation indices (NDVI, ARVI, SIPI, and GNDVI) were calculated. The range of the vegetation indices can be seen from the maps (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Vegetation indices (A= NDVI, B = ARVI, C = GNDVI, and D = SIPI)

Analysis of Vegetation Indices

Vegetation indices (VIs) are based on the characteristic reflection of plant leaves in the visible and near-infrared portions of light. It presupposes that healthy vegetation has a low reflection of visible light since it is strongly absorbed by leaf pigments (chlorophyll)

for photosynthesis. The four VIs were classified using different thresholds and further reclassified using Spatial Analyst Tools in ArcGIS 10.3 Software. The study area was broadly reclassified into a four-forest cover scheme. They are non-vegetation (i.e. bare land, roads, rivers, and small settlements), shrubs (short trees and grasses), secondary forest and primary forest (Figure 3). From Table 2, the phenological behaviors of the VIs under consideration vis-à-vis the area extent of the forest covers show the similarity in terms of spectral characteristics of the four reclassified vegetation indices. Looking at NDVI, Non-vegetation, (an aggregate of roads, rivers, and settlements) accounting for about 73.9287Km² (5 %). The shrubs occupied about 366.6834 Km² (25 %), while Secondary forest and Primary forest occupied about 646.1136Km²(45 %) and 356.9634 Km² (25 %) respectively. Analyzing the ARVI, the Non-vegetation area extent stood at about 57.4659 Km² (4 %), which is close to that of NDVI. Shrubs occupied about 296.2142 Km² (20 %), secondary forest stood at about 658.5786 Km² (46 %) and primary forest occupied about 431.4294 Km² (30 %). The statistics of SIPI are non-vegetation 93.1464 Km² (6 %), shrubs 460.7514Km² (32 %), secondary forest 606.8052 Km² (42 %) and primary forest 282.9861 Km² (20 %). For GNDVI analysis, Non-vegetation stood at 109.179 Km²(8 %), shrubs 453.4821Km²(31 %), secondary forest 605.3346 Km² (42 %) and primary forest 275.6934 Km²(19 %).

Figure 3: Reclassified VIs (A= NDVI, B = ARVI, C = SIPI, and D = GNDVI).

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Table 2: Statistics of reclassified Vis

FOREST COVER	NDVI		ARVI		SIPI		GNDVI	
	Area(km ²)	%						
NON-VEG	74.9287	5	57.4659	4	93.1464	6	109.179	8
SHRUBS	366.6834	25	296.2142	20	460.7514	32	453.4821	31
SEC.FOREST	646.1136	45	658.5786	46	606.8052	42	605.3346	42
PRY-FOREST	356.9634	25	431.4294	30	282.9861	20	275.6934	19
TOTAL	1443.6891	100	1443.6891	100	1443.6891	100	1443.6891	100

Overlay and Forest Health Analysis

The weighted sum analysis of the four vegetation indices produced a forest health map having a range between 0 and 24 (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Weighted sum of Vis

Figure 5: Forest Health Map

The map was reclassified into four categories, i.e. non-forest, unhealthy, moderately healthy and very healthy. Non-forest covered about 83.6604 km² (6 %) of the study area. Unhealthy forest occupied an area of about 354.4191 km² (25 %). The moderately healthy forest spanned across an area of about 638.7048km²(44 %). Lastly, the very healthy forest occupied about 366.9048 km² (25 %). The Strict Natural Reserve (Omo Biosphere) happens to be part of the very healthy forest.

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Conclusion

Just as humans carry out periodic medical checkups as pre-requisite for good health, forest health analysis has become very crucial to climate change mitigation. Remote sensing and GIS has leveraged on the availability of spatio-temporary data and cutting geospatial technologies for the study of forestry. The results of this study revealed that the VIs and reclassify tool of ArcGIS 10.3 can be very useful in phenological prognosis and the monitoring of forest health. The healthiest forest is approximately 25% of Omo forest. I, therefore, recommend that more attention is given to sustainable forest management.

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